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Research Article

EFFICIENCY OF EFFICIENT SIGMOIDOSCOPY DEPRESSION OPERATION FOR THE TREATMENT OF RECURRING AND PRIMARY ADENOIDAL COELENTERATE

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Abstract:

Objectives: This investigation work supported out to extravagant the efficacy of the ESDO (Efficient Sigmoidoscopy Depression Operation) in our organization as associated with the previous investigation works for the handling of the main and recurrent adenoidal coelenterate.

Methodology: This exploration work conceded out for a period of complete two years from December 2016 to November 2018 in the ENT Branch of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. In this exploration work, we selected one hundred and sixteen victims from both sexes with an assortment of age from eighteen to sixty year from the OPD of ENT Branch, with adenoidal coelenterate who experienced ESDO. Out of total one hundred and sixteen victims, 12.92% (n: 15) were existing with recurrent adenoidal coelenterate whereas 87.11% (n: 101) were existing with main NS. We assessed the victims scientifically. We achieved the adenoidal coelenterate before operation and calculated tomography MRI of nose as well as par-nasal depressions in each victim to assess the delay of disease and assess the clinical structure. We shadowed up the victims three monthly, six monthly and after one year. We evaluated the clinical indications of adenoidal coelenterate with the use of nasal Sigmoidoscopy at every appointment for track up.

Results: There were total one hundred and sixteen victims with recognized identification of adenoidal coelenterate. Between them, 64.72% (n: 75) were masculine victims & 35.34% (n: 41) victims from feminine gender. The average age of the male victims was 39.12 years and the average age of the female victims was 36.71 years. Only 12.95% (n: 15) victims industrialized recurrent disease in entire one year.

Conclusion: There is continuously partiality to the ESDO as a main treatment modality for recurring and primary adenoidal coelenterate. There can be enhancement in symbols with condensed probabilities of recurrent of the disease in better than ninety percent victims of this sickness.

Key Words: modality, symptoms, ESDO, adenoidal coelenterate, surgery, para-nasal depressions.

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INTRODUCTION:

The drip formed growths or growths in para-nasal depressions are nasal tumors. Their growth can be in the all areas of para-nasal depressions but greatest preferred places are the central meatus and osteomeatal complex areas. These difficulties have connection with the aversions and contagions for extended time mainly fungoid sinusitis. Mainstream of the people with adenoidal coelenterate present with anosmia, rhinorrhea, sneezing and post-nasal trickle. They can have connotation with the DNS (Deviated Nasal Septum). Generally current adenoidal steroid droplets are much effective in release from the connected indications. Occasionally, there is also medicine of the universal steroid sequences for very small terms. But in the most thoughtful cases, operation is the best selection to release the victims and for the development in their superiority of lifespan.

There is damage of attraction in outdated nasal polypectomy as of the high reappearance degree. Ankema has exposed that though twelve weeks treatment with the use of fluticasone propionate adenoidal drips reduced the obligation of the sinus operation in victims of adenoidal coelenterate and chronic rhino sinusitis but there was necessity of operation in fourteen out of twenty seven victims after the operation [1]. In current era, ESDO is the best choice for the treatment of such complication with high rate of accuracy and low recurrent degree. Damm has specified the enhancement in the QoL in eighty five percent victims with a regular continuation period of 31.74 years. The foundation of this investigation work was to assess the efficacy of ESDO in the treatment of primary and recurrent adenoidal coelenterate in our organization with assessment to the printed exploration mechanism in the earlier.

METHODOLOGY:

This exploration work conceded out for a period of complete two years from December 2016 to November 2018 in the ENT Branch of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. The moral group of the organization gave the authorization to comportment this investigation work. We comprised one hundred and sixteen victims from both sexes having assortment of age from eighteen to sixty years with recorded

diagnosis of adenoidal coelenterate. We did not include the victims suffering from other serious complications or diseases like HTN (Hypertension), DM (Diabetes Mellitus) and victims with very young age or in their late ages. We used the convenient sampling method for the selection of the victims. Surgery inclusion standard was basing upon the positive results of adenoidal coelenterate in the victims with the use of computed tomography and nasal endoscopy.

We applied the standard steps of the surgery to every patient depending upon the extension of the complication. Every patient underwent ESDO under GA (General Anesthesia). We obtained the consent from every patient after explaining them the purpose of this research work. We carried out the follow-up after surgery at first week, second weeks, 1st month, 3rd month, 6th month and one year by authors of this working on this study. We defined the recurring disease as a state of adenoidal coelenterate that appeared among victims who were recovered after surgery and occurred in later follow up period We prescribed the nasal steroid drops to all the victims as well as antibiotics after the surgical intervention. We also gave antifungal medicines to some victims. We evaluated all the victims through nose endoscopy after surgery and assessed the associated minor complication on every follow up visit.

RESULTS:

The average age of the male victims was 39.10 years and average age of the female victims was 36.70 years. Total one hundred sixteen victims with recorded diagnosis of adenoidal coelenterate were the part of this research work. There were 64.70% (n: 75) male and 35.30% (n: 41) female victims with a range of age from 18.0 to 60.0 years. Approximately 75.0% victims were present with anosmia. All the victims were present with different degrees of obstruction in nasal cavity. We staged the adenoidal coelenterate in three categories like polyps restricted to only middle meatus, polyps getting into inferior meatus and polyps touching the nasal cavity's floor. We placed the 72.0% victims in Stage-2 and 28.0% victims in Stage-3. We performed computed tomography and nasal endoscopy for every patient.

Table - 1: Demographic characteristics of the victims (n=116)

Characteristics		No / Mean	Percent / SD
Mean Age	Male	39.1	3.03
	Female	36.7	4.22
Gender	Male	75	64.7

We examined all the victims with the use of the nasal endoscope on their every visit for follow-up. We did not note any serious complication after the surgery. We dealt the minor issue like crusting & adhesions at the very moment. We also carried out the radiological grading of adenoidal coelenterate with the use of computed tomography. Out of one hundred and sixteen victims who were regularly followed-up only 12% (n: 17) victims were the cases with reoccurrence of complication.

Table-II : CT Scan & Endoscopy results

Outcomes		No	Percentage
Anosmia / Hyposmia		64.7	75%
Type of cases	recurrent case	17	12%
	non- recurrent cases	99	88%
Nasal Polyposis	up to middle meatus	-	-
	reaching inferior meatus	84	72%
	reaching Nasal Cavity	32	28%

DISCUSSION:

It stated the high recurrence rate of ADENOIDAL COELENTERATE with simple polypectomy. Messer Kling [3] Nasal polyps are without pain, soft, non-cancerous developments on the passage of nasal cavity and sinuses. There can be easy removal of the nasal polyps through surgery, restricting the passage of nose. With the use of the medicines and traditional surgical procedures, there can be recurring of the polyps in 3 out of four victims after a mean duration of four years [4]. Dalzeik invented the mucosal sparing method with the utilization of endoscope for this surgery. He emphasized on the removal of the key regions of obstruction to permit the normal function[5]. Stamberger justified the procedure of ESDO by discussing that nose & anterior ethmoids are accountable for most of the infections of maxillary & frontal [6]. Kenedy used the term of ESDO to elaborate the endoscopic method of sinus surgery for therapy of adenoidal coelenterate [7]. Suzuki also examined very low complication rat of only 0.50% after ESDO. Lildholdt also recommended the nasal steroid drops after the surgery. Follow-up for long term shows that ESDO is a surgical procedure of choice for victims suffering from ADENOIDAL COELENTERATE. Senior [8]. Steward stated high rate of improvement of symptoms in the victims suffering from severe condition of disease with the use of ESDO. We faced no serious complication during the surgery [10] has stated the symptom's improvement in 91.60% victims treated with ESDO within an average follow up duration of 7.80 years. The findings of this research work is much comparable with the case works of international level hence it

showed that ESDO in the better treatment modality for primary as well as recurring adenoidal coelenterate. Bhata Charyya N [11] and Satish N [12] stated that it is very successful and secure method with very low rate of morbidity as well as high rate of improvement in QoL of the victims. Bolger WE [13] has stated that ESDO is most beneficial surgical method with the improvement of mucociliary transport by the reduction in inflammation, edema and formation of polyp. Both technologies of ESDO and CT scan have extended the indications for the sinus surgery in accordance with findings of Emma [14]. This kind of surgical intervention is necessary for the severe cases of adenoidal coelenterate. There is also increase utilization of the recent technology of image-guided endoscopic surgery in lessening all concerns about major veins, brain and eyes.

CONCLUSION:

This modality is very effective and secure with very low rate of morbidity and very low rates of related complications. There are very less recurring rates of adenoidal coelenterate with increase in the improvement of symptoms and QoL (Quality of Life) in greater than ninety percent victims. For the therapy of adenoidal coelenterate, ESDO is one among the preferred modality.

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